

Sexist Bullshit Bingo

Do you keep hearing the same old things at faculty meetings? Here is a way to change all of that!

How to play: Check off each block when you hear these words during a faculty meeting on appointments. When you get five blocks horizontally, vertically, or diagonally, stand up and shout **SEXIST BULLSHIT!!**

This is an opportunity we can't miss	She overlaps with us too much	His overlaps will build on our strengths	She wouldn't really fit here	She's good but not a star
Her work isn't that exciting	She just didn't impress me	He'd be a great addition	The good women are all taken	The experts think he's great
Women don't work in this area	He visited here and really fit in	Stanford will get him if we don't	We can't let diversity affect quality	Put more women on the committee
You're a woman and you were hired	A woman supported him too	I've supported a woman in the past	He's just the best in this area	I've never heard of her
He isn't a star but fits a critical need	I've known him for years	I don't understand her work	You call to see if there are good women	Gender never even entered the picture

Testimonials from satisfied players:

"I had only been in the meeting for five minutes when I won." -Jane W. – Boston University

"My attention span at meetings has improved dramatically." -Mary T. – Florida State

"What a gas. Meetings will never be the same for me after my first win." -Joanne P. - MIT

"The atmosphere was tense in the last meeting as 6 of us waited for the 5th box." –Sue F. Denver U.

"The dean was stunned as eight of us screamed ' Sexist Bullshit' for the third time in 2 hours." - Kathleen L. – Penn State